

**Repositioning of
Non-antimicrobial drugs
(anti-inflammatory drugs)
to Act as
Antibiotic**

Supervised

By

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Antibiotic resistance

1. History of resistance beginning

Antibiotic has been discovered in 20th after discovery of infectious agent in the late 19th but unfortunately, the evolution of antibiotic resistance has been appeared over the last 20 years due to human misuse of antibiotic.

Which give an opportunity to microbes to exploit every source of resistance genes, and every means of horizontal genes transition to develop multiple mechanism of resistance, for the most antibiotic exist in the market which is the main cause of going back to pre-antibiotic era, that obligate us to discover a way to overcome this resistance by other techniques such as, re-positioning of non antibiotic drugs and other approaches. (1,2)

2. General mechanisms of antibiotic resistance in bacteria

Figure1

1. interference with cell wall synthesis (e.g., β -lactams and glycopeptide agents)
2. inhibition of protein synthesis (macrolides and tetracyclines)
3. interference with nucleic acid synthesis (fluoroquinolones and rifampin)
4. inhibition of a metabolic pathway (trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole)
5. disruption of bacterial membrane structure (polymyxins and daptomycin) (3,4,5)

3.Bacteria that developed resistance

3.1.ESCHERICHIA COLI (E.COLI)

- **First Documented:** 1895
- **Illness Caused:** Diarrhea, Urinary Tract Infection, Meningitis
- **Antibiotic Resistance:** High
- **Virulence:** Worrying
- Most *E.coli* is completely harmless and survives in the human digestive system. However, some strains of *E.coli* can cause serious illness and most commonly lead to severe food poisoning as well as meningitis and infections.

Figure 2

A high level of resistance to antibiotics has been found across several strains of *E.coli* and while it is rare to find these strains causing illness, it is another concerning example of a bacteria that has the potential to cause problems if our use of antibiotics goes unchecked.

- In previous studies, the antibiotic resistance profiles of 515 non-pathogenic *E. coli* isolates obtained from food products of animal origin (n = 47) and from fecal samples of healthy animals (n = 177) and humans (n = 291) were studied. Seventeen *E. coli* isolates from those groups (four from food, eight from animals, and five from humans) showed a multiple-antibiotic-resistant phenotype (resistance to nalidixic acid, ampicillin, rifampin, chloramphenicol, sulfamethoxazole, streptomycin [STR] and tetracycline). All 17 of these isolates were used in the present work to detect different mechanisms of antibiotic resistance and to study the antibiotic resistance genes inside integrons and the relevance of the *mar* locus in the multiple-antibiotic-resistant phenotype (6,7,8,9, 10)

3.2.PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA

First Documented: 1872

Illness Caused: Pneumonia, Various Infections

Antibiotic Resistance: Medium

Virulence: Worrying

Quick to mutate (**there was a study in 1994 to 1997, suggested that efflux resistance mechanisms are more common in isolates from CF(cystic fibrosis) patients than in strains from urine and wounds from non-CF patients, in which mutations in (gyrA and parC) sequence dominate)** and adapt to counter different antibiotic treatments,

Pseudomonas aeruginosa shows an innate ability to develop resistance to antibiotics. Described as ‘opportunistic’ because it primarily affects humans that are already critically ill, this bacteria can cause serious complications in the treatment of **AIDS, cancer or cystic fibrosis patients.**

While it isn’t a massive threat to humanity currently, this bacteria will become an increasing threat over the next few years.(6,7,11)

Figure 3

3.3.STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS (MRSA)

First Documented: 1884

Illness Caused: Pneumonia, Flesh Eating Disease

Antibiotic Resistance: Medium

Virulence: Dangerous

More commonly known as MRSA (which stands for Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*), this ‘superbug’ is very easily spread **through human contact**

and can cause a range of illnesses from **skin disorders to deadly diseases like meningitis and pneumonia.**

The symptoms of MRSA depend on where you're infected.

Figure 4

Figure 5 mechanism of Staphylococcal resistance

Mechanisms of resistance

Staphylococcal resistance to penicillin is mediated by *blaZ*, the gene that encodes β -lactamase. This predominantly extracellular enzyme, synthesized when staphylococci are exposed to β -lactam antibiotics, hydrolyzes the β -lactam ring, rendering the β -lactam inactive

Most often, it causes mild infections on the skin, like sores or boils. But it can also cause more serious skin infections or infect surgical wounds, the bloodstream, the lungs, or the urinary tract

Most often treated with Penicillin type antibiotics, by 1960, 80 % of hospital samples were antibiotic resistant. A concerted effort in tracking the disease and improving hygiene measures in hospitals has seen cases of MRSA fall by 84.7 % in the UK between 2003 and 2011, proving that prevention is often the best form of defense against bacteria. (6,7,12,13)

4.Approaches that have been used to treat antibiotic resistance since it appear

First we must mention that the hospitals are the main places that at which transmission of antibiotic resistant bacteria from person to person take place through

- contact with contaminated hands of hospital staff
- contact with contaminated surfaces such as door handles, over-bed tables and call bells
- contact with contaminated equipment, such as stethoscopes and blood pressure cuffs

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Figure 6 proportion between prescribed against non-prescribed antibiotics and the rise of resistance

And that does not mean that antibiotic resistance did not take place in community

Most of antibiotics drugs are used in the outpatient setting, and there were studies estimate that half of outpatient antimicrobial are prescribed for inappropriate indications, **such as viral illnesses**

And this was the outcome of surveillance done in this study Rates of prescriptions for the 'common cold', upper-respiratory-tract infections (URIs) and bronchitis in children and adolescents.

Which approve that also community have large influence in antibiotic resistance

4.1.simple approaches without any intervention

- Minimize unnecessary prescribing and over-prescribing of antibiotics.
- Complete the entire course of any prescribed antibiotic so that it can be fully effective and not breed resistance.

- Practice good hygiene such as hand-washing and use appropriate infection control procedures.

4.2.Ways to prevent transmission of organisms, including antibiotic resistant bacteria, are:

- Wash hands before and after food handling, going to the toilet and changing nappies.
- Cover your nose and mouth when coughing and sneezing.
- Use tissues to blow or wipe your nose.
- Dispose of tissues properly, either in the rubbish or toilet.
- Do not spit.
- Stay at home if you are unwell and cannot manage the normal requirements of your day.
- Do not send children to child care, kindergarten or school if they are unwell.
- If you are prescribed antibiotics, take the entire course – do not stop because you are feeling better.
- If you continue to feel unwell, go back to the doctor.
- Avoid use of products that advertise they contain antibiotics, or are antibacterial or antimicrobial, unless advised to do so by your health professional.

It has been found also that not only physition and community were misusing the antibiotics but also in agriculture field it was used for varies reasons which made World Health Organization (WHO) take an action and but some roles to be applied in this field

4.3. Agriculture sector

To prevent and control the spread of antibiotic resistance, the agriculture sector can:

- Only give antibiotics to animals under veterinary supervision.
- Not use antibiotics for growth promotion or to prevent diseases in healthy animals.
- Vaccinate animals to reduce the need for antibiotics and use alternatives to antibiotics when available.
- Promote and apply good practices at all steps of production and processing of foods from animal and plant sources.
- Improve biosecurity on farms and prevent infections through improved hygiene and animal welfare.

(14,15,16)

5-Approches that have been used in treatment of antibiotic resistance by different intervention

5.1- bacteriophage natural enemies of bacteria

It was discovered independently by Frederick Twort in 1915 & Fèlix d'Herelle in 1917 before penicillin and they were discovered by chance in a patient who unexpectedly recovered illness (due to harmful bacteria) the scientist discovered back than the phages in his stools so they use phage in treatment of Dysentery & cholera BUT unfortunately this therapy did not stay for a long time since penicillin discovered which make study over phage and viruses eclipsed BUT true study of viruses started at 1940 were the first image of phage were obtained by electronic microscope, and they found that

each type of phage has a specific landing pad at which attachment to bacteria occur and then, phage inject its DNA into bacteria to make more copies of it and during this process it consume the bacteria machinery and also produce toxic chemicals that rupture the bacterial host from inside out.

Figure 7 life cycle of Bacteriophage

5.1.1.ADVANTAGES OF PHAGES OVER ANTIBIOTICS

1- phages are specific bacteria so it will not kill any other beneficial bacteria (normal micro-flora in gut) that have important roles for EXAMPLE Lacto-bacillus acidophilus which produce lactic acid and hydrogen peroxide in the intestine during the digestive process as it breaks down food

Which is killed by antibiotics especially the wide spectrum ones

2- phage have the ability to kill antibiotic- resistant bacteria due to it is harder for bacteria to develop resistance to phage as it is do with antibiotics since phages do not work through stopping a specific process but it destroy bacteria's cell wall and cell membrane and kill bacteria through forming holes from inside out

In addition to that phages have tools that can digest the bio-film (thick layer of viscous material that protect bacteria from antibiotic) so it is useful in case of bio-film forming bacteria.

5.1.2.WHY AREN'T PHAGES USED ?!

1- phage are more difficult to prepare cleaning and to produce , it we have to grow large quantity of bacteria that is the natural host of phages BUT the major concern is when obtaining phages if there is still dead bacteria bodies it can cause deadly immune response called SAPSIS or its concentration is too low so therapy will be in-eficacious.

2- phages take longer time to give outcome compared to antibiotics ,phages can only infect few species so , the doctor first have to discover the identity of bacteria than see if there is specific phage for it or not and if not doctor have to search for new phage which is time consuming process and not all patient have time unlike wide spectrum antibiotics doctor doesn't need to check first identity of bacteria

5.1.3.WHERE ARE PHAGE THERAPY NOW ?!

After bacteria have developed resistance to antibiotics the interests in phages therapy renewed, that the European Union invested 5 Million Euro in a project that study the use of phages to prevent skin infections

Figure 8 phagoburn

in burn victims the FDA approved Listhield™, a food additive that contains phages to kill

Listeria monocytogenes, one of the most virulent food-borne pathogens that can cause meningitis

Currently many clinical trials using phages to treat or prevent bacterial infections such as MRSA & Tuberculosis are still undergoing trials. (17,18)

5.2. CARB-X (Resistant Bacteria – Antibiotic Combat) accelerator

A recent national plan addressing the global problem of antibiotic resistance recognizes new antibiotics development as one of its five goals. Launched in March 2015, the White House National Action Plan to Combat Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria aims to move at least two new vaccines, non-traditional therapeutics and antibiotic drug candidates from pre-clinical tests to clinical trials by 2020, among other outcomes.

But Joe Larsen, PhD, one of the leaders behind the Combating Antibiotic Resistant Bacteria Biopharmaceutical Accelerator, thinks that his public-private partnership will be able to create much more than two new products. Launched in July, the accelerator, known as CARB-X, will provide companies with promising new antibiotics the help they need to navigate research and development through four accelerators.

The accelerators offer assistance such as access to funding, business development support and feedback on commercial feasibility of new drugs. (19)

5.3. molecules that block toxin formation in bacteria

The molecules cling to a toxin-making protein found across Gram-positive bacterial species, called **AgrA**, rendering it ineffective, when they made this study in **Western Reserve University** they found out that, when treating mice with the therapeutic molecules effectively cured infections caused by methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). *S. aureus* known for its ability to overcome even the most potent antibiotics. And in this study they are suggesting that it may be for immunocompromised patients, by using combination therapy with the molecules and a low-dose antibiotic may be in order. The antibiotic in the combination could be one to which the bacteria are resistant in monotherapy,

because our small molecules enhance the activity of conventional antibiotics, such as penicillin

Concept of this study is to eliminate toxins, which frees up the immune system to eliminate bacterial pathogens instead of antibiotics.

And this what the authors said about the possibility that this molecule may have broad spectrum efficacy

(These results indicate broad-spectrum efficacy against Gram-positive pathogens," wrote the authors. Added Shoham, "We have proven efficacy not only against MRSA but also against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* which is notorious for clogging catheters, *Streptococcus pyogenes* that causes strep throat, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and other pathogens.") (20)

5.4 – A biochemical approach (small molecular attachment) that helps conventional antibiotics penetrate and destroy their target

And in this study that have been done by Stanford chemists few of them (Alexandra Antonoplis, a graduate student in chemistry and co-lead author with fellow chemistry graduate student Xiaoyu Zang & Wender, who is also a member of Stanford Bio-X, the Stanford Cancer Institute, and Stanford ChEM-H.

The attachment of a small molecule , known as r8, helps guide antibiotics through a bacterium's outer defenses and encourages them to enter the bacteria, that penetration help kill bacteria, such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, or MRSA, that doctors would otherwise struggle to stop.

The current first-line treatment for MRSA has been in use since 1958.

That first-line treatment, the antibiotic vancomycin, can keep MRSA from spreading in some cases by preventing the construction of new bacterial cell walls, thus preventing the bacteria from reproducing.

But vancomycin is largely useless against two of the bacteria's key defenses. First, MRSA has a tendency to form biofilms, colonies of the bacteria embedded within a protective membrane that drugs have a hard time penetrating. Second, MRSA bacteria can lie dormant for extended periods, during which time vancomycin doesn't work—meaning doctors need an antibiotic that can stick around until MRSA bacteria start to wake up.

To test vancomycin with the attached r8, dubbed V-r8, the team pitted both it and vancomycin against MRSA in a free-floating state and in biofilms. When

bacteria were floating around freely in a liquid, both vancomycin and V-r8.
(21)

5.5. A role for topical silver treatment in treating topical antibiotic resistance.

This study have been done in 1998 were silver have been used in 3 different methods to check difference in efficacy 3 methods of applying silver to wounds: as a liquid (silver nitrate), incorporated in a cream (silver sulfadiazine) and as a dressing coating (silver-coated dressings).

Moreover, they found that Silver demonstrated to be effective at killing the antibiotic-resistant strains tested. The silver-coated dressing was particularly rapid at killing the tested bacteria and was effective against a broader range of bacteria. Silver may be a useful prophylactic or therapeutic agent for the prevention of wound colonization by organisms that impede healing, including antibiotic-resistant bacteria.(22)

5.6. Antimicrobial dressings: Comparison of the ability of a panel of dressings to prevent biofilm formation by key burn wound pathogens

In this approach, Antimicrobial medicated dressings (AMD) are often used to reduce bacterial infection of burns and other wounds. And in a previous study that demonstrated good anti-biofilm properties of acetic acid (AA) so in this complementary study they compared the *in vitro* anti-biofilm activity of a range of AMDs and non-AMDs to AA.

They found that there is : Large variation exists in the ability of AMD to prevent biofilm formation and colonisation of wounds. A standardised *in vitro* methodology should be developed for external parties to examine and compare the efficacies of commercially available AMDs, along with robust clinical randomised controlled trials. This is essential for informed clinical decision-making and optimal patient management. (23)

5.7. Photodynamic Therapy Associated with Conventional Endodontic Treatment in Patients with Antibiotic-resistant Microflora: (A Preliminary Report)

This study reports the antimicrobial effect of **photodynamic therapy (PDT)** combined with **endodontic**((is the study of biology, morphology, physiology, a etiology, and diagnosis of pathology, and treatment of dental pulp and periradicular tissue)) treatment in patients with necrotic pulp infected with micro-flora resistant to a previous antibiotic therapy.

In this study

All the patients had at least 1 microorganism resistant to antibiotics. PDT used polyethylenimine chlorin(e6) as a photosensitizer and a diode laser as a light source (P = 40 mW, t = 4minutes, E = 9.6 J). Endodontic therapy alone produced a significant reduction in numbers of microbial species but only 3 teeth were free of bacteria, whereas the combination of endodontic therapy with PDT eliminated all drug-resistant species and all teeth were bacteria-free.

The use of **PDT added to conventional endodontic treatment** leads to a further major reduction of microbial load. PDT is an efficient treatment to kill multi-drug resistant microorganisms. (24)

5.8. Removal of antibiotics in conventional and advanced wastewater treatment: Implications for environmental discharge and wastewater recycling

This study is aiming for removal of antibiotics from treated water (recycled water) by, detection of remaining antibiotic in **both ways**

- Conventional (activated sludge" thick, soft, wet mud or a similar viscous mixture of liquid and solid components, especially the product of an industrial or refining process. ")
- Advanced (microfiltration / reverse osmosis) waste water treatment plant

Were they detect

- dominant antibiotics detected in wastewater influents were cephalexin, ciprofloxacin, cefaclor, sulphamethoxazole and trimethoprim. Results indicated that both treatment plants significantly reduced antibiotic concentrations with an average removal rate from the liquid phase of 92%. However, antibiotics

were still detected in both effluents from the low-to-mid
ng L⁻¹ range

- Effluent from the activated sludge, WWTP included ciprofloxacin, sulphamethoxazole, lincomycin and trimethoprim.
- Antibiotics identified in microfiltration/reverse osmosis product water included naladixic acid, enrofloxacin, roxithromycin, norfl, oleandomycin, trimethoprim, tylosin, and lincomycin.
- Certain traditional parameters, including nitrate concentration, conductivity and turbidity of the effluent were assessed as predictors of total antibiotic concentration, however only conductivity demonstrated any correlation with total antibiotic concentration.
- There is currently a lack of information concerning the effects of these chemicals to critically assess potential risks for environmental discharge and water recycling. (25)

5.9.Synergism between conventional antibiotic and anti-biofilm forming agent

- In this review article, Synergistic Effects between Conventional Antibiotics and two-Aminoimidazole-(Derived Anti-biofilm Agents), are an emerging class of small molecules that possess the ability to inhibit and disperse bio-films across bacterial order, class, and phylum.
- And this synergistic effect between a 2-aminoimidazole/triazole conjugate and antibiotics was tested upon dispersing pre-established bio-films, culminating with a 3-orders-of-magnitude increase of biofilm dispersion toward *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilms.
- Furthermore, in this article they were able to document that the 2-aminoimidazole/triazole conjugate will also re-sensitize multidrug-resistant strains of bacteria to the effects of conventional antibiotics, including **methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*(MRSA) and multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii***. (26)

5.10.Reuse of Daptomycin after proper clinical trials

- Daptomycin is a novel cyclic lipopeptide antibiotic that provides rapid bactericidal activity against gram-positive pathogens in vitro, including methicillin-susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus*, methicillin-resistant *S. aureus*, vancomycin-resistant *S. aureus*, penicillin-resistant *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and ampicillin- and vancomycin-resistant enterococci.
- Daptomycin was discovered by Eli Lilly in the early 1980s (and known then as LY146032); however, concerns about skeletal muscle toxicity observed at dosages as low as 6 mg/kg per day in divided doses led to voluntary suspension of clinical trials in 1991
- But in 1997the increasing need for new agents against gram-positive pathogens, Cubist Pharmaceuticals licensed the worldwide rights for daptomycin from Eli Lilly and initiated clinical trials in 1999 that used a daily dose of 4–6 mg/kg, on the basis of data from pharmacodynamic studies.
- In September 2003, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved daptomycin at the 4 mg/kg dose for the treatment of complicated skin and skin-structure infections (cSSSIs) caused by susceptible strains of *S. aureus* (including methicillin-resistant strains), *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, *Streptococcus dysgalactiae* subspecies *equisimilis*, and *Enterococcus faecalis* (vancomycin-susceptible strains only)

In this study they suspected that mechanism of action :

Figure 9 Daptomycin mechanism of action

- To act at the cytoplasmic membrane, binding to the membrane via a calcium-dependent insertion of its lipid tail.
- Current understanding of its mechanism of action suggests that it forms an ion-conduction structure, resulting in an efflux of potassium (and possibly other ions) with an associated dissipation of the ion concentration gradient.

In conclusion they found out that

- Notably, the activity of daptomycin is dependent on the presence of calcium ions, which directly impacts the conditions required for in vitro susceptibility testing .
- Daptomycin has several pharmacodynamic characteristics that make it an attractive alternative to currently available agents for treating drug-resistant gram-positive bacterial infections. In vitro studies demonstrate a rapid bactericidal effect against drug-resistant gram-positive pathogens. It is active in a concentration-dependent manner and has a significant postantibiotic effect, allowing a once-daily administration regimen. (27)

5.11.Charged metallopolymer s that exhibit synergistic effects against MRSA

Antimicrobial Metallopolymer s and Their Bioconjugates with Conventional Antibiotics against Multidrug-Resistant Bacteria

In this review article they introduce a class of charged metallopolymer s that exhibit synergistic effects against MRSA by efficiently inhibiting activity of β -lactamase and effectively lysing bacterial cells. Various conventional β -lactam antibiotics, including penicillin-G, amoxicillin, ampicillin, and cefazolin, are protected from β -lactamase hydrolysis via the formation of unique ion-pairs between their carboxylate anions and cationic cobaltocenium moieties.

Figure 10. Synergistic effects against MRSA of charged

These discoveries could provide a new pathway for designing macromolecular scaffolds to regenerate vitality of conventional antibiotics to kill multidrug-resistant bacteria and superbugs. (28)

5.12. Peptide antibiotics

- Currently there is great interest in peptide antibiotics, especially the cationic peptides. Thousands of such molecules have been synthesised and just a few are entering clinical trials. Because they kill bacteria quickly by the physical disruption of cell membranes, peptide antibiotics may not face the rapid emergence of resistance. (29)
- are produced by several species including insects, other animals, micro-organisms and synthesis, are a critical component of the natural defense system.
- They can protect against a broad array of infectious agents, such as bacteria, fungi, parasite, virus and cancer cells.

- AMPs have a good future in the application in pharmaceuticals industry and food additive. (30)

5.13.The antibiotic-lock technique for therapy of ‘highly needed’ infected catheters

- The antibiotic-lock technique consists of filling the catheter lumen with an antibiotic solution and allowing it to dwell for a period of time, in order to sterilize the device.
- However, many questions about this therapeutic method remain to be resolved, including appropriate concentration of antibiotics, duration of treatment, and whether or not concomitant systemic antibiotic therapy is necessary. Prospective studies comparing the antibiotic-lock technique with conventional treatment are needed.(31)

5.14.Mushroom extract antibacterial activity

This work aimed to screen the antimicrobial activity of aqueous methanolic extracts of 13 mushroom species

1. (*Agaricus arvensis* (Shaeff.:Fr.)→ Horse Mushroom ,
2. *Agaricus bisporus* (Lange) Imbach→ White Mushroom ,
3. *Cantharellus cibarius* L.:Fries → Chanterelle ,
4. *Fistulina hepatica* (Schaeff.:Fr) →Beefsteak Fungus ,
5. *Lactarius deliciosus* (L.) Gray →Saffron Milk Cap,
6. *Lactarius salmonicolor* (Heim y Leclair) ,
7. *Lepista nuda* (Bull. ex Fr.) Cooke →Wood Blewit ,
8. *Leucopaxillus giganteus* (Sowerby) Singer→ Giant Leucopax,
9. *Mycena rosea* (Schumach.) Gramberg→Rosy Bonnet ,
- 10.*Ramaria botrytis* (Pers.:Fr.) Ricken →Cauliflower Coral ,
- 11.*Russula delica* (Fr.) →Milk-white Brittle Gill ,
- 12.*Sarcodon imbricatus* (L.) P. Karst → Shingled Hedgehog ,
- 13.*Tricholoma portentosum* (Fr.) Qué. → Dingy Agaric

, collected in Bragança, against several clinical isolates obtained in Hospital Center of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro, Portugal.

And they found that out of those 13 mushroom species (*Fistulina hepatica*, *R. botrytis* and *R. delica* are the most promising species as antimicrobial agents) (32)

5.15. Quorum Sensing: Cell-to-Cell Communication in Bacteria

Quorum sensing (QS) is a signaling system that occurs in the pathogenic kingdom to sense its own population density and synchronize the expression of the virulence gene via the secretion of small, diffusible signal molecules, such as *N*-acyl-homoserine lactone (AHL), termed autoinducers. (68)

Autoinducers play a critical role in triggering virulence gene expression in QS-dependent pathogens, such as in the production of rotting enzyme.

Interfering with the microbial QS system by quorum quenching (QQ) has been suggested as a potential strategy for disease control (69) because QQ aims to shut down the virulence expression in pathogenic bacteria rather than restrict cell growth and has shown potential to overcome drug toxicities, complicated super-infection and antibiotic resistance (70). The interest in enzymatic function for protecting against microbial infection has intensified in recent years. QQ enzymes have been identified in a number of bacteria that have shown considerable promise as quorum quenchers since AHL-lactonase AiiA was first identified from *Bacillus* species to attenuate virulence in *Erwinia carotovora*.

QQ can be developed as a technique for disrupting the ability of a pathogen to sense its cell density and disable or diminish the capability of triggering the virulent expression. This capability ensures that the host has time to eradicate the pathogens naturally through normal immune system function, resulting in overcoming the pathogenic infection. Because it is different from conventional antibiotic therapy, which kills bacteria by interfering with DNA, RNA or protein synthesis, leading to the emergence of antibiotic-resistant superbugs, QQ is a promising approach that may lead to the development of very effective next generation antibacterial drugs based on interfering with bacterial communication to block QS-mediated pathogenic infection.

The physiological function of most QQ enzymes is not consistently clear, but these enzymes are found in QS and non-QS microbes (71). Co-culturing the QQ producer with QS-dependent microbial pathogens has been shown to attenuate QS related activities. This study aimed to elucidate the enzymatic protection for host diseases in the QS system and its application in resistance against microbial diseases, **primarily focusing on**

- (1) the biodiversity of organisms with the potential to quench the QS signals;
- (2) the enzymatic degradation of the QS signals by QQ enzymes;
- (3) the function and characteristics of the enzymes with QQ activity;

- (4) the molecular phylogenesis of QQ enzymes in the QS system;
- (5) the enzymatic degradation of global signal molecules in the cell-cell signal transduction pathway
- (6) the application of antimicrobial agents of enzymatic protection in controlling microbial disease by interfering with the QS system, which expounds on the degradation of the autoinducers to block microbial attack. It is important that the enzymatic protections are completely non-disruptive to the environment and that their use will lead to a reduction in the application of chemicals.

5.15.a.Mechanism of QS

QS is found in both Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. It can be species specific or non-specific i.e. operate between bacterial cells of different species. The signal molecules involved in QS are found to be diverse in nature. Mostly the molecules employed are small (< 1000 Da) organic molecules or peptides with 5- 20 amino acids. In case of Gram negative bacteria the signaling molecules generally used are N-acylhomoserine lactones (AHLs), 2-alkyl-4- quinolones (AQs), long chain fatty acids and fatty acid methyl esters. Gram positive bacteria employ linear, modified or cyclic peptides such as the auto inducing peptides (AIPs). Both Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria are found to use auto inducer-2 for QS which is a group of interconvertible furanones derived from dihydroxypentanedione (DPD) (72)

5.15.b.Quorum Sensing in Bacteria

Quorum sensing has been described in different species of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, and it plays vital roles in diverse cellular functions(73) .Gram-positive systems typically use secreted oligopeptides and two-component systems, which consist of membrane-bound sensor kinase receptors and cytoplasmic transcription factors that direct alterations in gene expression. Four common features are found in nearly all known Gram-negative quorum sensing systems (74). First, the autoinducers in such systems are acyl-homoserine lactones (AHLs) or other molecules that are synthesized from S-adenosylmethionine (SAM), and they are able to diffuse freely through the bacterial membrane. Second, autoinducers are bound by specific receptors that reside either in the inner membrane or in the cytoplasm. Third, quorum sensing typically alters dozens to hundreds of genes that underpin various biological processes. Fourth, in a process called autoinduction, autoinducer-driven activation of quorum sensing stimulates the increased synthesis of the autoinducer, which establishes a feed-forward loop that is proposed to promote synchronous gene expression in the population (75).

5.15.b.1.Quorum Sensing in Gram-Negative Bacteria

The first described quorum-sensing system is that of the bioluminescent marine bacterium

Vibrio fischeri, and it is considered the paradigm for quorum sensing in most gram-negative bacteria (Nealson & Hastings 1979). *V. fischeri* colonizes the light organ of the Hawaiian squid *Euprymna scolopes*. In this organ, the bacteria grow to high cell density and induce the expression of genes required for bioluminescence. The squid uses the light provided by the bacteria for counterillumination to mask its shadow and avoid predation (Visick et al. 2000). The bacteria benefit because the light organ is rich in nutrients and allows proliferation in numbers unachievable in seawater.

Two proteins, LuxI and LuxR, control expression of the luciferase operon (*luxICDABE*) required for light production (Figure 1).

Figure 1
Quorum sensing in *Vibrio fischeri*; a LuxIR signaling circuit. Red triangles indicate the autoinducer that is produced by LuxI. OM, outer membrane; IM, inner membrane.

Figure 11 Quorum sensing in *Vibrio fischeri* a LuxIR signaling circuit. Red triangles indicate the autoinducer that is produced by LuxI. OM, outer membrane; IM, inner membrane.

LuxI is the autoinducer synthase, which produces the acyl-homoserine lactone (AHL) autoinducer 3OC6-homoserine lactone (Figure 2a and Eberhard et al. 1981, Engebrecht & Silverman 1984), and LuxR is the cytoplasmic autoinducer receptor/DNA-binding transcriptional activator (Engebrecht et al. 1983).

Figure 12 LuxI is the autoinducer synthase.

Following production, the AHL freely diffuses in and out of the cell and increases in concentration with increasing cell density (Kaplan & Greenberg 1985). When the signal reaches a critical, threshold concentration, it is bound by LuxR and this complex activates transcription of the operon encoding luciferase (Stevens et al. 1994).

Importantly, the LuxR-AHL complex also induces expression of luxI because it is encoded in the luciferase operon. This regulatory configuration floods the environment with the signal. This creates a positive feedback loop that causes the entire population to switch into “quorum-sensing mode” and produce light.

A large number of other gram-negative proteobacteria possess LuxIR-type proteins and communicate with AHL signals (Manfield & Turner 2002). These systems are used predominantly for intraspecies communication as extreme specificity exists between the LuxR proteins and their cognate AHL signals. LuxI-type proteins link and lactonize the methionine moiety from S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) to particular fatty acyl chains carried on acyl-acyl carrier proteins (More et al. 1996, Parsek et al. 1999). A diverse set of fatty acyl side chains of varying length, backbone saturation, and side-chain substitutions are incorporated into AHL signals; these differences are crucial for signaling specificity (**Figure 2a and Fuqua 1999**).

Figure 12 LuxI is the autoinducer synthase

Structural studies of LuxI-type proteins indicate that each possesses an acylbinding pocket that precisely fits a particular side-chain moiety (Gould et al. 2004, Watson et al. 2002). This structural feature apparently confers specificity in signal production. Thus, each LuxI protein produces the correct signal molecule with high fidelity. There are some LuxI-type proteins that produce multiple AHLs, although it is not clear if all are biologically relevant (Marketon et al. 2002). The structures of LuxR proteins suggest that LuxR proteins also possess specific acylbinding pockets that allow each LuxR to bind and be activated only by its cognate signal (Vannini et al. 2002, Zhang

et al. 2002b). Hence, it appears that in mixed-species environments in which multiple AHL signals are present, each species can distinguish, measure, and respond only to the buildup of its own signal. Importantly, bacteria rarely rely exclusively on one LuxIR quorum sensing system.

Rather, bacteria use one or more LuxIR systems, often in conjunction with other types of quorum-sensing circuits. Mechanisms must exist to prevent premature activation of LuxIR-type quorum sensing circuits because both the signal and the detector are synthesized and interact in the cytoplasm (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1
Quorum sensing in *Vibrio fischeri*; a LuxIR signaling circuit. Red triangles indicate the autoinducer that is produced by LuxI. OM, outer membrane; IM, inner membrane.

Figure 11 Quorum sensing in *Vibrio fischeri* a LuxIR signaling circuit. Red triangles indicate the autoinducer that is produced by LuxI. OM, outer membrane; IM, inner membrane.

One such mechanism, evidenced by the LuxR homologue TraR in the plant pathogen *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*, is the stability of LuxR-type proteins increases upon AI binding. In the absence of autoinducer, TraR has a half-life of a few minutes. However, in the presence of AHL, the half-life of TraR increases to over 30 minutes (Zhu & Winans 1999). The crystal structure of TraR predicts that AHL binding is required for folding of the nascent polypeptide (Zhang et al. 2002b), and indeed radiolabeled TraR was stabilized only when its cognate AHL was added prior to labeling of the protein (Zhu & Winans 2001). Hence, only when AHL accumulates to a significant concentration (both outside and inside the cell) can TraR bind it, fold, and initiate the quorum sensing

cascade. Another mechanism that prevents “short-circuiting” of LuxIR systems is active export of AHL signals (Pearson et al. 1999). When a significant concentration of signal has accumulated, which is indicative of high cell density, diffusion into the cell overwhelms export and thus engages the circuit. AHLs with long acyl side chains are thought to require active export to transverse the bacterial membrane (Pearson et al. 1999).

5.15.b.2.Quorum Sensing in Gram-positive Bacteria

Gram-positive bacteria communicate using modified oligopeptides as signals and “twocomponent”- type membrane-bound sensor histidine kinases as receptors. Signaling is mediated by a phosphorylation cascade that influences the activity of a DNA-binding transcriptional regulatory protein termed a response regulator. Similar to the mechanisms by which gram-negative bacteria use LuxIR quorum-sensing systems, each gram-positive bacterium uses a signal different from that used by other bacteria and the cognate receptors are exquisitely sensitive to the signals’ structures. Thus, as in LuxIR systems, peptide quorum-sensing circuits are understood to confer intraspecies communication.

Peptide signals are not diffusible across the membrane, hence signal release is mediated by dedicated oligopeptide exporters. In most cases, concomitant with signal release is signal processing and modification. While the biochemistry underlying these events is poorly defined, it is known that most peptide quorum-sensing signals are cleaved from larger precursor peptides, which then are

modified to contain lactone and thiolactone rings, lanthionines, and isoprenyl groups (Ansaldi et al. 2002, Booth et al. 1996, Mayville et al. 1999, Nakayama et al. 2001). Many gram-positive bacteria communicate with multiple peptides in combination with other types of quorum-sensing signals. A fascinating example of peptide quorum sensing exists in *Staphylococcus aureus*, which is normally a benign human commensal but becomes a deadly pathogen upon penetration into host tissues (reviewed in Tenover & Gaynes 2000).

S. aureus uses a biphasic strategy to cause disease: At low cell density, the bacteria express protein factors that promote attachment and colonization, whereas at high cell density, the bacteria repress these traits and initiate secretion of toxins and proteases that are presumably required for dissemination (reviewed in Lyon & Novick 2004). This switch in gene expression programs is regulated by the Agr quorum-sensing system (Figure 3).

Figure 3
Using a two-component response regulatory system, *Staphylococcus aureus* detects and responds to an extracellular peptide. Small red circles indicate the AIP. P2 and P3 designate the promoters for *agrBDCA* and *RNAIII*, respectively.

Figure 13 Using a two-component response regulatory system, *Staphylococcus aureus* detects and responds to an Extracellular peptide. Small red circles indicate the AIP. P2 and P3 designate the promoters for *agrBDCA* and *RNAIII*, respectively.

The system consists of an autoinducing peptide of *Staphylococcus aureus* (AIP) (Figure 2b) encoded by *agrD* (Ji et al. 1995) and a two-component sensor kinase-response regulator pair, AgrC and AgrA, respectively (Novick et al. 1995).

b

Oligopeptide autoinducers

AIP-I (*S. aureus*)

AIP-II (*S. aureus*)

AIP-III (*S. aureus*)

AIP-IV (*S. aureus*)

ADPITRQWGD	ComX (<i>B. subtilis</i>)
ERGMT	CSF (<i>B. subtilis</i>)
EMRLSKFFRDFILQRKK	CSP (<i>S. pneumoniae</i>)

Figure 14 an autoinducing peptide of *Staphylococcus aureus* (AIP)

The AgrB protein exports and adds the thiolactone ring modification to *S. aureus* AIPs (Saenz et al. 2000). Binding of the AIP to AgrC leads to phosphorylation of AgrA. Phospho-AgrA induces the expression of a regulatory RNA termed RNAIII, which represses expression of cell adhesion factors while inducing expression of secreted factors (Novick et al. 1993). Activated AgrA also induces expression of the agrBDCA. This results in increased AIP levels, which ensures that the entire population switches from the low-cell-density to the high-cell-density state (Novick et al. 1995).

S. aureus strains are classified on the basis of the sequence of their thiolactone-containing AIP. At present, four different AIPs (Figure 2b and Dufour et al. 2002), and thus four different groups of *S. aureus*, are known. Surprisingly, each AIP specifically activates its cognate AgrC receptor but inhibits activation of all others by competitive binding to the non-cognate receptors (Lyon et al. 2002b).

Figure 14 an autoinducing peptide of *Staphylococcus aureus* (AIP)

Thus, each AIP inhibits activation of the virulence cascade in the other three groups of *S. aureus* while not affecting the other groups' growth. Coinfection with two different *S. aureus* groups results in intraspecies competition; the *S. aureus* group that first establishes its quorum-sensing cascade outcompetes the other group. Consistent with this idea, purified AIP II attenuates virulence of a Group I *S. aureus* in a mouse infection model (Mayville et al. 1999). Thus, in *S. aureus*, quorum sensing allows dissemination of closely related progeny while inhibiting the spread of nonkin. Clinical analyses show that each *S. aureus* group is the primary causative agent of a specific type of *S. aureus* disease. This suggests that cell-cell communication has been instrumental in establishing a specific niche for each "strain" (Novick 2003). The codivergence of the signal-receptor pairs occurring in these bacteria may be one molecular mechanism underlying the evolution of new bacterial species.

Streptomycetes are a diverse family of gram-positive soil-dwelling bacteria that are of clinical relevance because they are a major biological reservoir of secondary metabolites, many of which are used as antibiotics (reviewed in Chater & Horinouchi 2003). Streptomycetes use γ -butyrolactones (**Figure 2c**) as autoinducers and control morphological differentiation and secondary metabolite production via quorum sensing. Their signals are intriguing because they are structurally related to AHL autoinducers. However, there has not yet been any report describing either cross-communication between or cross-inhibition of streptomycetes and Gram-negative bacteria that communicate with AHLs.(76)

C

Streptomyces γ -butyrolactones

A-factor (*S. griseus*)

Figure 15 Streptomycetes use γ -butyrolactones as autoinducers and control morphological differentiation

5.15.c.Applications of Quorum quenching in Research and Biotechnology

Naturally occurring quorum quenching processes are being tested as novel antimicrobial therapies. Over-expression of *aiiA* in tobacco and potato plants confers resistance to *E. carotovora*, which requires AHL – controlled virulence factor expression to cause disease (77).

Likewise, co-culture of *B. thuringiensis* decreased *E. carotovora* – mediated plant disease in an *aiiA* – dependent manner (78)

Mice treated with synthetic antagonists of *S. aureus* AIP show resistance to infection (79).

Similarly, purified halogenated furanones appear to attenuate virulence of bacteria in mouse models (80).

These and other examples predict that inhibition of quorum sensing offers an attractive alternative to traditional antibiotics because these strategies are not bactericidal and therefore the occurrence of bacterial resistance could be reduced (81).

Likewise, approaches aimed at promoting beneficial quorum sensing associations may enhance industrial scale production of natural or engineered bacterial products. Quorum quenching molecules have proved to be valuable

tools in addressing both the basic and the conceptual questions. Skin lesions on inoculated mice were reduced when AIP – II, the group – specific cell – to – cell communication signal produced by group – II *S. aureus*, was included in the inoculum mixture of group – I *S. aureus* bacterial cells (79). The experiment identified the key structural characteristics of the signals involved in activation and antagonism, and led to the design of a global inhibitor of the virulence response in *S. aureus* (80).

Since the discovery of the first quorum quenching enzyme encoded by *aiiA* the prokaryotic origin AHL – lactonases and AHL – acylases have been frequently used in investigations of the role of AHL signals owing to the convenience in cloning and expression. The role of AHL quorum sensing signalling in the regulation of virulence and other physiological roles in *Burkholderia thailandensis* and *E. amylovora* has been demonstrated by expression of the AHL – lactonases encoded by the *aiiA* homologues in these two pathogens (82, 83). The quorum quenching enzymes, along with other small naturally quorum quenchers and synthetic derivatives have been explored and evaluated as novel antimicrobial agents against different pathogens with promising outcomes. Expression of *AiiA* in transgenic potato and tobacco plants conferred strong resistance to the bacterial pathogen *E. carotovora*, which requires AHL quorum sensing signals to activate the expression of virulence genes[9]. Similarly, natural or recombinant AHL – lactonase producing bacterial strains, including *B. thuringiensis*, *Arthrobacter* species and *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, protected potato from *E. carotovora* infection when co – inoculated with the pathogen (82).

6- Re-positioning of non- antimicrobial drugs to be antimicrobial

It is looming concept for drug discovery progression and it is better than discovering a whole new drug that will pass the whole validation process of drug which is costly and time consuming and some surveys have shown that it takes 15 years and around US \$800 million including pre-clinical and clinical costs to bring a single drug into market and not only this but high manufacturing together with research and development costs may found to be loss if the new drug is withdrawn from market due to adverse drug reaction or toxicity .

A re-purposing or re-positioning old drug existing in the market where it is appeared originally in developing country which bring to them new therapies that provide a short cut way between laboratory and clinical trials where drug of known adverse drug reaction that may be benefit in another diseases than that drugs is assigned for, Example of those drugs that have been redeveloped or reassigned due, to other outcome to work against virus ,fungi and bacteria where about 500 drugs, and those non anti-microbial drugs have been found to either have a direct antimicrobial activity “antimicrobial of non antibiotics “ , synergistically increase efficiency of antibiotic drugs when given as combination or change of microorganism pathogenicity (competing with host for metabolic sources, destroying its cells or tissues or secreting toxins) ,or activity on the physiology such as modulating macrophage activity. (33, 34)

6.1.Categories of non-antibiotic drugs that have antimicrobial activity

Some non-antibiotics have a direct antimicrobial activity through various effects on bacterial and/or fungal cells, for example, membrane effects, metabolic alterations, DNA intercalation, adhesion suppression, etc. Others have an indirect antimicrobial activity as helper compounds or as immune system modulators.

Helper compounds are enabling further usage of conventional antibiotics by acting synergistically when co-administered or by reverting resistant microbial phenotype, for example, by altering the permeability of the membranes. Some helper compounds may inhibit replication of the plasmids that can carry resistance genes and even eliminate them from the cells. Immune system modulators help the host in fighting the infection, for example, by stimulating cytokine secretion from the T-cells, or by

potentiating the killing of the phagocytised microorganism inside of the macro-phage (35)

There are a lot of categories of non antibiotic drugs that have been found to have antimicrobial activity against gram positive bacteria or gram negative bacteria , Such an effect has been noticed for barbiturates, beta-adrenergic receptor antagonists, diuretic drugs, H1 antihistamines, mucolytic agents, nonsteroid anti-inflammatory drugs, proton pump inhibitors and psychotherapeutic drugs (36)

6.2.The category of interest and the core of our work is NSAID

NSAIDs (non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs) are a class of drugs are used to treat inflammation, mild to moderate pain, and fever.

This category have been observed and discovered to have antimicrobial activity since (1977 to 2003) but it was referred as non-antibiotic in 1992 .(37)

Although it is one category but each drug have different mechanism regarding the anti-microbial activity and that is what we have found through our research and our work by MIC method and we work over 6 drugs that will be discussed in details in the discussion part and those drugs are **(diclofenac , celecoxibe ,meloxicum, ketorolac, dexamethason ,paracetamol)**

1. Diclofenac

Anti-inflammatory mechanism

The antiinflammatory effects of diclofenac are believed to be due to inhibition of both leukocyte migration and the enzyme cyclooxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2), leading to the peripheral inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis.

Possible anti-microbial activity

Though much in-formations about the mechanism of activity is still not very clear, some have attributed it to be a result of the inhibition of DNA synthesis in bacterial cells (38)

2. Ketorolac

Anti -inflammatory mechanism

Ketorolac inhibits key pathways in prostaglandin synthesis which appears crucial to its mechanism of action. Although ketorolac is non-selective and inhibits both COX-1 and COX-2 enzymes, its clinical efficacy is derived from its COX-2 inhibition. The COX-2 enzyme is inducible and is responsible for converting arachidonic acid to prostaglandins that mediate inflammation and pain. By blocking this pathway, ketorolac achieves analgesia and reduces inflammation. Ketorolac is administered as a racemic mixture; however, the "S" enantiomer is largely responsible for its pharmacological activity (39,40)

Anti-microbial mechanism

There is no specific mechanism that provide that ketorolac have anti-microbial activity but it was found that it can suppress inflammation without exacerbating fungal ocular infection.(41)

3. Meloxicam

Anti -inflammatory mechanism

exert their actions by inhibiting cyclooxygenase (COX). It has recently been postulated that NSAIDs' antiinflammatory efficacy arises from inhibition of the COX-2 isoform of cyclooxygenase, whereas inhibition of the COX-1 isoform produces the troublesome and sometimes serious gastric and renal side effects of NSAIDs. (42)

Anti-microbial mechanism

Pseudomonas aeruginosa biofilm formation could be largely influenced by quorum sensing (QS) system, which is mechanism that bacteria use to coordinate their behavior. The *las* and *rhl* QS system is mediated by acyl-homoserine lactone (HSL) signals including C4-HSL and 3-oxo-C12-HSL, which could activate the transcriptional regulators LasR and RhlR, respectively. The genes regulated by LasR and RhlR could control the biofilm formation, motility phenotype, and other virulence genes.

found that meloxicam could significantly inhibit PAO1 bio-film formation in a dose-dependent manner at the concentration without influence on planktonic cell growth. Meloxicam could also significantly inhibit the

motilities, production of extra-cellular matrix, and expression of quorum sensing-related genes and virulence factors of PAO1(43)

4. Celecoxib(Celebrex)

Is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug widely used for the treatment of pain, fever, and inflammation.

Anti-inflammatory mechanism

- It specifically inhibits the enzyme cyclooxygenase-2 (COX2), thereby reducing the synthesis of pro-inflammatory prostaglandins.

Beyond its anti-inflammatory activity, celecoxib has been shown to possess antimicrobial activity against several microbial pathogens. In a group of study celecoxib was found to reduce the total fungal loading *Histoplasma capsulatum* infected mice. Further, celecoxib treatment also increased the survival rate of the mice infected with lethal dose of *H.capsulatum*

Found that it inhibited the growth of *Francisella tularensis* and *F. novicida*. In addition, it also exhibited antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*.

the spectrum of its activity against various clinical isolates of multidrug-resistant Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens.

Antimicrobial activity

- Mode of action of celecoxib was that the RNA, DNA, and protein synthesis inhibition were detected at concentrations significantly below the MIC.
- However, a secondary effect was also observed at higher concentration, with a clear dose-dependent disruption of [³H] glycerol incorporation indicating decreased lipid synthesis. Cell wall synthesis inhibition was evident only at a concentration above the MIC.(44,45)

7.Aim of our work

The aim of this project is to evaluate antimicrobial activity of anti-inflammatory drugs by using it against different species of bacteria in combination with antimicrobial drugs rather than discovery of new antimicrobial drugs with highly costs.

8.Material

This study was carried out in Department of Microbiology, College of pharmacy and drug manufacturing, Pharos University, Alexandria– Egypt, 2019

8.a)Materials:

Anti-inflammatory Drugs:

- 1) Meloxicam
- 2) Acetaminophen
- 3) Dexamethasone,
- 4) Diclofenac sodium,
- 5) celecoxib,
- 6) Ketorolac tromethamine

all these drugs were purchased from a local pharmacy **except Acetaminophen and Ketorolac tromethamine** they were obtained from **R&D department of Pharco B international pharmaceuticals** as pure powder form.

- Meloxicam as solution is obtained from Mobital ampules 15mg/1.5ml manufactured by Medical union pharmaceuticals. (Figure16)

- Dexamethasone as solution is obtained from Dexamethasone ampules 8mg/2ml manufactured by Amriya pharmaceuticals. Two ampules were used.(Figure 17)

- Diclofenac sodium as solution is obtained from Declophen ampules 75mg/3ml manufactured by Pharco pharmaceuticals.(Figure 18)

- Celecoxib as powder form is obtained from Celebrex hard gelatin capsules 100mg manufactured by Pfizer pharmaceuticals.(Figure 19)

8.b.Antibiotics used for the Kirby Bauer technique:

1. oxacillin (OX) 1 µg
2. Ofloxacin (OFX) 5 µg
3. Tobramycin (TOB) 10 µg
4. Ampicillin (AMP) 10 µg
5. Ceftriaxone (CRO) 30 µg
6. Imipenem (IPM) 10 µg

Figure 20 antibiotic disks

7. Sulfamethoxazole with trimethoprim (SXT) 25 µg
8. Cefoperazone 75 µg
9. Ciprofloxacin (CIP) 5 µg
10. piperacillin/tazobactam (TZP) 110 µg
11. Cefepime (FEB) 30 µg
12. moxifloxacin (MXF) 5 µg
13. Gentamicin (CN) 10 µg
14. Aztreonam (ATM) 10 µg
15. ceftiofloxacin (FOX) 30 µg
16. Rifampin (RA) 5 µg
17. Levofloxacin (LEV) 5 µg
18. Tetracycline (TE) 10 µg
19. Tetracycline (TE) 30 µg

Figure 21 antibiotic disks and its distribution

9. Methods & Results

Bacterial strains and reagents

Micro-organisms used were staphylococcus aureus, pseudomonas aeruginosa and E-coli that were obtained from a private lab.

9.1. Kirby Bauer technique

1. Staphylococcus aureus 2 isolates
2. Pseudomonas aeruginosa 2 isolates
3. E-coli

were tested against different antibiotic discs which were obtained from Oxoid.

The culture was swabbed homogeneously across plates and the antibiotic discs in known concentration were added in the plate .

The antibacterial activity was estimated based on size of inhibition zone formed around the well-seeded agar plates and the bacterial profile was determined.

Figure 22-kirby Bauer technique

Figure 23 Kirby Bauer technique

Results of this technique

Graph.1. Effect of all antibiotic discs against all chosen bacteria

Graph.2.1- Effect of all antibiotics against Staphylococcus aureus 1

Graph.3. 2- Effect of all antibiotics Against Staphylococcus aureus 2

Graph.4.3 Effect of all antibiotics against Pseudomonas aeruginosa 1

Graph .5.4.Effect of all antibiotics against Pseudomonas aeruginosa 2

Graph .6.5.Effect of all antibiotics against E.coli

9.2.Determination of MIC Minimum Inhibitory concentration by broth dilution technique

- Sterile micro-titer plates were used, the horizontal wells were labeled 1,2,3...12; while vertical ones were labeled A, B, C... G.
- The wells A2 to A12 received 100 µl of two-fold serially diluted stock solution of levofloxacin or 100 µl of sterile distilled water; while well A1 received 100 µl of sterile distilled water served as control.
- Final concentrations of antibiotic under test were ranging from 1000 to 0.9 µg/ml.
- And as for the tested anti-inflammatory agent serial two fold dilution of concentrated stocks were used **MIC is chosen as last clear well showing no growth**

Figure 24 Sterile micro-titer plate

Graph.7. 1-MIC in case of ketorolac with all chosen bacteria

Graph .8.2-MIC in case of Diclofenac with all chosen bacteria

Graph .9.3-MIC in case of Celecoxib against PS1&PS2 ,ST1&ST2

Graph .10.4-MIC in case of Meloxicam against PS1&PS2

Graph .11.Collection of effect of all anti-inflammatory drugs against chosen bacteria

Antimicrobial effect of NSAIDs

Graph .12.Effect of all drugs against P.aeruginosa1

Graph .13.Effect of all drugs against P.aeruginosa2

Graph .14. Effect of all drugs against ST.aureus1

Graph .15.Effect of all drugs against ST.aureus1

Graph.16.Effect of all drugs against ST.aureus2

9.3.Determination the effect of MIC of levofloxacin by checkerboard technique

- Sterile micro-titer plates were used, the horizontal wells were labeled 1,2,3...12; while vertical ones were labeled A, B, C... G.
- The wells A2 to A12 received 50 µl of two-fold serially diluted stock solution of levofloxacin and 50 µl of sterile distilled water; while well A1 received 100 µl of sterile distilled water served as control. Final concentrations of antibiotics under test were ranging from 1000 to 0.9 µg/ml.
- The wells B1 to B12 received 50 µl of two-fold serially diluted solution of levofloxacin and 50 µl of anti inflammatory agent solution

- The remaining series received the same two-fold serially diluted stock solution of the antimicrobial agent under test and for the series C, D, E, F and G respectively.
- Each of the 84 wells received 100 µl of sterile double strength nutrient broth inoculated with 10⁶ CFU/ml of each of the tested organisms and mixed gently.
- The plated were covered and incubated at 35- 37°C for 14 hours.
- The MIC was taken as the lowest antimicrobial agent concentration showing no growth turbidity. The combined activity of **Levofloxacin and anti-inflammatory** was calculated using activity index method (pillai et al.,2005) as follows:

$$\text{Activity Index} = \frac{\text{MIC of the antimicrobial agent in combination}}{\text{MIC of the antimicrobial agent alone}}$$

Effect of combination between anti-inflammatory drugs and chosen antibiotic levofloxacin

Graph.17.1- Diclofenac against staph1 in presence of levofloxacin

Graph.18.2-Diclofenac aginst ps1 in presence of levofloxacin

Graph.19.3-Celexcoxibat aginst staph1 in present of levofloxacin

Graph.20.4-Celexcoxibat aginst Ps1 in present of levofloxacin

Graph. 21.5-ketrolac against st2 in present of levofloxacin

Graph.22.6-ketrolac against Ps2 in present of levofloxacin

Graph.23.7-meloxicam against Ps1 in present of levofloxacin

Graph .24.8-meloxicam against st1 in present of levofloxacin

10.Discussion

1. Dexamethasone:

(Neher A. et al 2008) In study of Antimicrobial activity of dexamethasone and its combination with N-chlorotaurine, after long exposure of dexamethasone alone it showed bactericidal effect against *Streptococcus milleri*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Aspergillus flavus*. The combination of dexamethasone and N-chlorotaurine showed very strong antimicrobial effect and higher than N-chlorotaurine alone. This combination has high efficacy with low side effects, so it might be a promising therapeutic option. (46)

(Aquila Rodrigues et al 2017) In vitro study of Dexamethasone abrogates the antimicrobial and antibiofilm activities of different drugs against clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed that dexamethasone interfered with the antimicrobial activity “negative interference risks” of Gentamicin, Chloramphenicol, Oxacillin and Ceftriaxone. This doesn't mean that this impairment it might also occur in the living cells as it's more complicated as drug metabolism and distribution occur. (49)

(Abdullah DOĞAN et al 2017) In the study of an investigation of antibacterial effects of steroids showed that corticosterone showed inhibitory effect against *P. multocida* and beta-sitosterol against *Staphylococcus aureus*. After analyzing steroids according to the number of bacteria affected and the effective concentrations this showed that they don't have superior

antibacterial effect when compared to current drugs. We need more pharmacodynamics and

pharmacokinetic, in vitro and in vivo activity studies to be done as there are not enough evidence about the antibacterial activity of steroids against different types of bacteria whether positive or negative. (52)

(Wanderley Marques Bernardo et al 2012) statistical study of Effectiveness of the association of dexamethasone with antibiotic therapy in pediatric patients with bacterial meningitis it showed there is no benefit of the combination between dexamethasone and different antibiotics like cefotaxime, ampicillin/sulbactam, ampicillin /chloramphenicol, benzathine/penicillin with chloramphenicol and ceftriaxone .It didn't reduce mortality so it might be an example of Non-antibacterial effect of dexamethasone. (55)

(Michael T. Drbbin et al 2007) Dexamethasone does not alter in vitro antibacterial efficacy of gentamycin show that Dexamethasone does not alter the in vitro antibacterial activity against gentamycin for staphylococcus aureus and pseudomonas Pseudomonas aeruginosa. (57)

2. Paracetamol

(Ali Abdul Hussein S. AL-Janabi 2010) in vitro study of Antibacterial Activity of Ibuprofen and Acetaminophen, acetaminophen showed inhibitory effect against different types of bacteria like Escherichia coli, Salmonella typhi, Enterobacter cloacae, Klebsiella aerogenes, Paracoccus yeei, Staphylococcus Aureus , Bacillus subtilis at concentrations between 0.625 to 5mg/ml. the higher the concentration the wider the range of bacterial inhibition while at 0.321 mg/ml it didn't show any antibacterial effect against these species. (47)

(Amudat LAWAL et al 2007) Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activity of aspirin and paracetamol metal complexes showed that Paracetamol metal complexes (with nickel and ferric) were found to have antibacterial effect. Paracetamol complex with ferric "Fe(Par)₂Cl₃" has the he greatest inhibitory effect against E. coli while "Ni(Par)₂Cl₂" have the lowest inhibitory effects at different concentrations. (50)

(ADEROJU A. OSOWOLE et al 2014) Synthesis, Characterization and antibacterial properties of some heteroleptic metal (II) complexes of

paracetamol and vanillin, The in-vitro antibacterial activity of the same paracetamol metal complexes against *Bacillus cereus*, *E. coli*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella oxytoca* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Cobalt(II) complex exhibited a broad spectrum antibacterial activity against these bacteria. (53)

Another article by (Desalegn Amenu 2014) Antimicrobial activity of medicinal plant extracts and their synergistic effect on some selected pathogens showed that Paracetamol has antibacterial activity especially against *staphylococcus aureus* and *pseudomonas aeruginosa*. (56)

3. Celecoxib:

(Hayder M. Al-kuraishy 2011) Assessment and evaluation the antibacterial activity of selective cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors: In vitro study showed inhibitory effects of celecoxib on *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* but It was resistant to of *pseudomonas aeruginosa*.(48)

(Madhavi Annamanedi et al 2014) Celecoxib Sensitizes *Staphylococcus aureus* to Antibiotics in Macrophages by Modulating SIRT1 showed that celecoxib alone didn't have an inhibitory effect on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria. celecoxib in combination with ampicillin managed infection and inflammation caused due to *S. aureus* in macrophage model via activation of SIRT1. There was a decrease in bacterial survival time (51)

(Madhavi Annamanedi et al 2017) Celecoxib Enhances the Efficacy of Low-Dose Antibiotic Treatment against Polymicrobial Sepsis in Mice and Clinical Isolates of ESKAPE Pathogens showed that Combining celecoxib with ampicillin helps clearing the bacterial load while acting as anti-inflammatory. It controls the anti-inflammatory response by activation of SIRT1, it inhibits the inflammatory protein COX- and NF- κ B pathways in polymicrobial sepsis in the animal model.

In vitro activity the combination of celecoxib and ampicillin showed antibacterial activity against isolates of ESKAPE pathogens (*Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter* species) by the same

mechanism. This is a promising good co-treatment to overcome the antimicrobial drug resistance pathogens. (54)

(Younis W. et al 2015) Repurposing celecoxib as topical antimicrobial agent showed that In vivo activity combination using a mouse model of MRSA (multidrug-resistant *S. aureus*.) skin infection it showed synergistic effect with the topical antimicrobial agents used 1 or 2% celecoxib, 2% fusidic acid, or clindamycin it reduces the bacterial load in the wounds (45)

4. Meloxicam

Anti-inflammatory mechanism

exert their actions by inhibiting cyclooxygenase (COX). It has recently been postulated that NSAIDs' antiinflammatory efficacy arises from inhibition of the COX-2 isoform of cyclooxygenase, whereas inhibition of the COX-1 isoform produces the troublesome and sometimes serious gastric and renal side effects of NSAIDs. (42)

Anti-microbial mechanism

Pseudomonas aeruginosa biofilm formation could be largely influenced by quorum sensing (QS) system, which is mechanism that bacteria use to coordinate their behavior. The *las* and *rhl* QS system is mediated by acyl-homoserine lactone (HSL) signals including C4-HSL and 3-oxo-C12-HSL, which could activate the transcriptional regulators LasR and RhlR, respectively. The genes regulated by LasR and RhlR could control the biofilm formation, motility phenotype, and other virulence genes.

found that meloxicam could significantly inhibit PAO1 bio-film formation in a dose-dependent manner at the concentration without influence on planktonic cell growth. Meloxicam could also significantly inhibit the motilities, production of extra-cellular matrix, and expression of quorum sensing-related genes and virulence factors of PAO1 (43)

In the current study for, meloxicam it showed no activity against *pseudomonas aeruginosa* in tested concentration (>300 U_g /ml) and showed an MIC of 18.75 U_g/ml against *staphylococcus aureus* tested strains and it had no effect on levofloxacin activity against tested microorganisms were no change in MIC was noticed

(Pengfei She, et al in 2018 Feb; 7) in a study that take about inhuibitory effect of Meloxicam against biofilm formation they found that it inhibits biofilm that formed by *P. Aeruginosa* (58)

(Hayder M. Al-kuraishy et al in 2013) proved that meloxicam has an inhibitory effects on Staph.aureus, Escherichia coli but show no activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (59)

5. Diclofinac NA

Anti-inflammatory mechanism

The antiinflammatory effects of diclofenac are believed to be due to inhibition of both leukocyte migration and the enzyme cylooxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2), leading to the peripheral inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis.

Possible anti-microbial activity

Though much in-formations about the mechanism of activity is still not very clear, some have attributed it to be a result of the inhibition of DNA synthesis in bacterial cells (38)

(Umaru, et al in , 2009) in a study that take about Antimicrobial activity of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs they found that diclofenac have antimicrobial activity and referred to it as non-antibiotics drug

diclofenac has the greatest inhibitory effect against biofilm formation in combarison to Celecoxib, and meloxican (60)

(Sherin Jose Chockattu 2018) diclofenac NA were shown to have anti-bacterial effect against *E. Faecali* (61)

(Rohini Padma et al in 2015) diclofenac Na has antimicrobial activity against 397 invitro And 45 invitro strains of bacteria including Escherischia coli, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (62)

(Fulwah YahyaAlqahtani et al in 2019) diclofinac loaded chitosan nano particle show higher antimicrobial activity than diclofenac alone against *Staphylococcus aureus* (63)

(Agostinho Alves de Lima e Silva et al in 2018) diclofenac has in vitro synergism effect in combination with streptomycin for different species of Gram positive and Gram-negative bacteria (64)

In the current study MIC of diclofenac Na against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* range between 28.125 Ug/ml and 112.5 Ug/ml and for *Staphylococcus aureus* ranged between 56.25 ug/ml and 7.8 ug /ml and for *E coli* it was 112.5 ug/ml and in combination with levofloxacin it was noticed that a decrease in MIC of levofloxacin were noticed by 2 fold against *Staph aureus* that was converted to antagonism y decreasing diclofenac concentration up to sub MIC level 16 fold antagonism was noticed and only an antagonism up to 32 fold in case of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was notice

6. Ketorolac

Ketorolac inhibits key pathways in prostaglandin synthesis which appears crucial to its mechanism of action Although ketorolac is non-selective and inhibits both COX-1 and COX-2 enzymes, it's clinical efficacy is derived from its COX-2 inhibition. The COX-2 enzyme is inducible and is responsible for converting arachidonic acid to prostaglandins that mediate inflammation and pain. By blocking this pathway, ketorolac achieves analgesia and reduces inflammation .Ketorolac is administered as a racemic mixture; however, the " S " enantiomer is largely responsible for its pharmacological activity (39,40)

Anti-microbial mechanism

There is no specific mechanism that provide that ketorolac have anti-microbial activity but it was found that it can suppress inflammation without exacerbating fungal ocular infection.(41)

In our study ketorolac showed MIC of 31.25 ug/ml and 250 ug/ml against *Pseudomonas* strains , and of 62.5 ug/ml against *Staph aureus* while an MIC of >100 ug/ml in case of *E coli* .and in case of combination with levofloxacin it had no effect on MIC of levofloxacin where no change in MIC was noticed

(Andrew S. Hendrix et al in 2016)ketorolac (acetic acid derivative class) did not show inhibitory effect against *Staphylococcal* cytotoxicity toward (1) osteoblastic cells (65)

(Silvia Rossetti et al in 2012 Jun)they used 40 *S. epidermidis* strains isolated from postoperative endophthalmitis ketorolac has shown significant effect on biofilm ODs of the *S. endophthalmitis* when they compared untreated and treated strains with ketorolac they found that Ketorolac has an activity against *S. epidermidis* biofilm formation **(66)**

(Patel, Dharti. et al in 2012) an effective combination of ketorolac with moxifloxacin has an antimicrobial activity and can be estimated by Uv visible spectroscopy **(67)**

11.Conclusion

- From the presented work we conclude that anti-inflammatory drugs represent a very successful candidate as antimicrobial agent
- Future investigation of all anti-inflammatory drugs and other drug categories against local isolates is a must

12.Recommendation

- Topical use in combination of antibiotic either as ocular drops or as local gel for wound healing is recommended to bypass toxicity and therapeutics indices problems

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